

BISINGULYAR INTEGRALNING BA'ZI BIR XOSSALARI VA ULARNING TATBIQLARI

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada jamlanuvchi funksiyalar fazosida bisingulyar integral uchun Zigmund tipidagi tengsizlik olindi. Bu tengsizlik asosida integral operatorga nisbatan invariant banax fazosi qurildi. Keyin esa bu fazoda chiziqli bo'lmagan integral tenglamaning yechimining mavjud va yagonaligi isbot qilindi.

Quyidagi bisingulyar integralni qaraymiz.

$$\tilde{u}(x_1, x_2) = \int_{a_1}^{a_2} \int_{b_1}^{b_2} \frac{u(s_1, s_2)}{(s_1 - x_1)(s_2 - x_2)} ds_1 ds_2,$$

bu yerda $u \in L_p^{loc}(\Delta)$, $\Delta = (a_1, a_2; b_1, b_2)$, $p > 1$

Quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz.

$$L_p^{loc}(a_1, a_2, b_1)$$

$$= \{u - o'lchovli | \forall \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi > 0, \xi_1 + \eta_1 \leq a_2 - a_1 = l_1, \xi \in (0, l_2], l_2 = b_2 - b_1, u \in L_p[a_1 + \xi_1, a_2 - \eta_1, b_1 + \xi, b_2]\}.$$

$$L_p^{loc}(a_1, a_2, b_2)$$

$$= \{u - o'lchovli | \forall \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi > 0, \xi_1 + \eta_1 \leq a_2 - a_1 = l_1, \xi \in (0, l_2], l_2 = b_2 - b_1, u \in L_p[a_1 + \xi_1, a_2 - \eta_1, b_1, b_2 - \xi]\}.$$

Quyidagi funksiyalarni kiritamiz.

$$\Omega_{p,1}(u, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) = \left(\int_{a_1 + \xi_1}^{a_2 - \eta_1} \int_{b_1}^{b_2 - \xi} |u(x_1, x_2)|^p dx_1 dx_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{p}},$$

$$\Omega_{p,2}(u, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) = \left(\int_{a_1 + \xi_1}^{a_2 - \eta_1} \int_{b_1}^{b_2 - \xi} |u(x_1, x_2)|^p dx_1 dx_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{p}},$$

$$\omega_{p,1}(u, \delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) = \sup_{h \in E} \left(\int_{a_1 + \xi_1}^{a_2 - \eta_1} \int_{b_1 + \xi}^{b_2 - h} |u(x_1, x_2 + h) - u(x_1, x_2)|^p dx_1 dx_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{p}},$$

$$\omega_{p,2}(u, \delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) = \sup_{h \in E} \left(\int_{a_1+\xi_1}^{a_2-\eta_1} \int_{b_1}^{b_2-h-\xi} |u(x_1, x_2 + h) - u(x_1, x_2)|^p dx_1 dx_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

bu yerda $p > 1, E = \{h: 0 < h \leq \min\{\delta, l_2 - \xi\}\}$.

2.1. - teorema. $u_i \in L_p^{loc}(a_1, a_2, b_i)$ $p > 1, \xi_i^i \in (0, l_2], i = 1, 2$ bo'lsin. U holda mos integrallar integrallanuvchi bo'lganda quyidagi tengsizliklar o'rinli.

$$\begin{aligned} & \Omega_{p,i}(\tilde{u}_i, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi^i) \leq \\ & \leq C \left[\frac{1}{\xi_1^{\frac{1}{q}}} \int_0^{\frac{\xi_1}{2}} \int_0^{\frac{l_2}{2}} \frac{\Omega_{p,i}(u_i, t_1, \frac{l_1}{2}, t_2)}{t_1^{\frac{1}{p}} t_2^{\frac{1}{p}} (t_2 + \xi^i)^{\frac{1}{q}}} dt_1 dt_2 + \frac{1}{\eta_1^{\frac{1}{q}}} \int_0^{\frac{\eta_1}{2}} \int_0^{\frac{l_2}{2}} \frac{\Omega_{p,i}(u_i, \frac{l_1}{2}, t_1, t_2)}{(t_1 t_2)^{\frac{1}{p}} (t_2 + \xi^i)^{\frac{1}{q}}} dt_1 dt_2 \right. \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{\xi_1^{\frac{1}{q}}} \int_0^{\frac{\xi_1}{2}} \int_0^{\frac{\xi^i}{2}} \frac{\omega_{p,i}(u_i, t_1, \frac{l_1}{2}, t_2, \frac{\xi^i}{2})}{t_1^{\frac{1}{p}} t_2} dt_1 dt_2 + \frac{1}{\eta_1^{\frac{1}{q}}} \int_0^{\frac{\eta_1}{2}} \int_0^{\frac{\xi^i}{2}} \frac{\omega_{p,i}(u_i, \frac{l_1}{2}, t_1, t_2, \frac{\xi^i}{2})}{t_2 t_1^{\frac{1}{p}}} dt_1 dt_2 \\ & \quad \left. + \beta(\xi^i) \Omega_{p,j}\left(u_j, \frac{l_1}{2}, \frac{l_1}{2}, \frac{l_2}{3}\right) \ln \frac{l_2}{\xi^i} \right] \end{aligned}$$

bu yerda

$$\beta(\xi^i) = \begin{cases} 1, & x_2 \in (0, \frac{l_2}{3}] \\ 0, & x_2 \in (\frac{l_2}{3}, l_2] \end{cases}$$

Bisingulyar integral operator uchun invariant fazo.

\bar{G} orqali mos ravishda $\{\xi_1, \eta_1, 0 < \xi \leq l_2, \xi_1 + \eta_1 \leq l_1\}$ va $\{0 < \delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi, \xi_1 + \eta_1 \leq l_1\}$ da aniqlangan musbat $(\varphi(\xi_1, \eta_1, \xi), \psi(\delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi))$ funksiyalar juftini belgilaymiz.

Bu funksiyalar ξ_1, η_1, ξ argumentlar bo'yicha kamayuvchi, $\psi(\delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi)$ funksiya δ bo'yicha deyarli o'suvchi $\frac{\psi(\delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi)}{\delta}$ deyarli kamayuvchi hamda $\delta \rightarrow 0$ da $\psi(\delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) \rightarrow 0$.

$(\varphi_1, \psi_1) \in \bar{G}$ bo'lsin. $H_{\varphi_1 \psi_1}^{p, b_1}$ orqali $L_p^{loc}(a_1, a_2, b_1)$ dagi shunday jamlanuvchi u funksiyalarni to'plamini belgilaymizki, bunda

$$\begin{aligned} & \exists C_1, C_2 > 0, \Omega_{p,1}(u, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) \leq C_1 \varphi_1(\xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) \\ & \omega_{p,1}(u, \delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) \leq C_2 \psi(\delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi) \end{aligned}$$

shartlar bajarilsin.

$H_{\varphi_1 \psi_1}^{p, b_1}$ fazoda normani quyidagicha kiritamiz:

$$\|u\|_{H_{\varphi_1 \psi_1}^{p, b_1}} = \max \left\{ \sup_{\xi_1, \eta_1, \xi} \frac{\Omega_{p,1}(u, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi)}{\varphi(\xi_1, \eta_1, \xi)}, \sup_{\delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi} \frac{\omega_{p,1}(u, \delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi)}{\psi(\delta, \xi_1, \eta_1, \xi)} \right\}$$

$H_{\varphi_1 \psi_1}^{p, b_1}$ fazo bu norma bo'yicha banax fazosi bo'ladi.

X_1 va X_2 lar biror chiziqli X fazodagi Banax fazolari bo'lsin. X_1 va X_2 larning arifmetik yig'indisini $X_1 + X_2$ orqali belgilaymiz, ya'ni

$$X_1 + X_2 = \{x \in X | \exists x_1 \in X_1, \exists x_2 \in X_2, x = x_1 + x_2\}$$

$X_1 + X_2$ da normani quyidagicha kiritamiz.

$$\|x\|_{X_1+X_2} = \inf_{\{x_1 \in X_1, x_2 \in X_2, x = x_1 + x_2\}} \max\{\|x_1\|_{X_1}, \|x_2\|_{X_2}\}$$

Bu norma bo'yicha $X_1 + X_2$ fazo Banax fazosi bo'ladi.

Ta'rif X_1, X_2, Y_1, Y_2 lar Banax fazolari, M, N chiziqli fazolar, $X_1, X_2 \subset M, Y_1, Y_2 \subset N$ va Y_1^0, Y_2^0 lar N dagi Banax fazolari bo'lsin.

Agar $AX_1 \subset Y_1 + Y_2^0, AX_2 \subset Y_2 + Y_1^0$ va $A: X_1 \rightarrow Y_1 + Y_2^0$ chegaralangan, $A: X_2 \rightarrow Y_2 + Y_1^0$ chegaralangan bo'lsa, A chiziqli operator $X_1 + X_2$ ni $Y_1 + Y_2$ ga ko'chirib,

(Y_1^0, Y_2^0) juft bo'yicha chegaralangan deyiladi. (Y_1^0, Y_2^0) bo'yicha chegaralanganlik,

A operatorning $X_1 + X_2$ ni $Y_1 + Y_2$ ga ko'chirib, chegaralanganlik tushunchasi bilan bir xildir.

\bar{G}_0 orqali \bar{G} dagi shunday (φ, ψ) funksiyalar to'plamini olamizki, $\forall \xi \in (0, l_2], \forall \xi_1, \eta_1 \in (0, l_1]$ da quyidagi integrallar yaqinlashuvchi bo'lsin.

$$\int_0^{l_1} \int_0^{l_2} \frac{\varphi\left(t_1, \frac{l_1}{2}, t_2\right)}{(t_1 t_2)^{\frac{1}{p}} (t_2 + \xi)^{\frac{1}{q}}} dt_1 dt_2, \int_0^{l_1} \int_0^{l_2} \frac{\varphi\left(\frac{l_1}{2}, t_1, t_2\right)}{(t_1 t_2)^{\frac{1}{p}} (t_2 + \xi)^{\frac{1}{q}}} dt_1 dt_2$$

$$\int_0^{l_1} \int_0^{l_2} \frac{\psi\left(t_1, \frac{l_1}{2}, t_2, \frac{\xi}{2}\right)}{t_1^{\frac{1}{p}} t_2} dt_1 dt_2, \int_0^{l_1} \int_0^{l_2} \frac{\psi\left(\frac{l_1}{2}, t_1, t_2, \frac{\xi}{2}\right)}{t_1^{\frac{1}{p}} t_2} dt_1 dt_2$$

Quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$H_{\ln \frac{2l_2}{\xi^2}, \frac{\delta}{\delta + \xi^2}}^{p, b_1} = M_1^{0, p}, H_{\ln \frac{2l_2}{\xi^2}, \frac{\delta}{\delta + \xi^2}}^{p, b_2} = M_2^{0, p}$$

$\bar{G}_0 H_p$ orqali \bar{G}_0 dagi shunday funksiyalar to'plamini belgilaymizki, quyidagi shartlar bajarilsin.

$$1. \int_0^{\xi_1} \int_0^{l_2} \frac{\varphi(t_1, t_2)}{(t_1 t_2)^{\frac{1}{p}} (t_2 + \xi)} dt_1 dt_2 = O(\varphi(\xi_1, \xi))$$

$$2. \int_0^{\xi_1} \int_0^{\xi} \frac{\psi\left(t_1, t_2, \frac{\xi}{2}\right)}{t_1^{\frac{1}{p}} t_2 (t_2 + \delta)} dt_1 dt_2 = O(\psi(\xi_1, \delta, \xi))$$

$$3. \psi(\xi_1, \delta, \xi) = O(\varphi(\xi_1, \xi))$$

$$4. \frac{\delta}{\delta + \xi} \varphi(\xi_1, \xi) = O(\psi(\xi_1, \delta, \xi))$$

2.2. - teorema. $(\varphi_1, \psi_1), (\varphi_2, \psi_2) \in \bar{G}_0 H_p$ bo'lsin. U holda \tilde{u} operator ni $H_{\varphi_1 \psi_1}^{p, b_1} + H_{\varphi_2 \psi_2}^{p, b_2}$ o'zini - o'ziga o'tkazadi va $(M_1^{0, p}, M_2^{0, p})$ bo'yicha chegaralangan bo'ladi.

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